
Prerequisites for efficiency of human resources management in crisis situations (from classic theories to a new vision)

Stoyko Stoykov *¹ A; Valentin Vasilev ² B

*Corresponding author: ¹ Dr of Economic Science, e-mail: stoykods@abv.bg, ORCID: 0000-0002-4885-713X

² PhD, e-mail: valentin.vasilev@vusi.bg, ORCID: 0000-0002-0074-9578

^A SWU “Neofit Rilsi”, Blagoevgrad, Bulgaria

^B Higher School of Security and Economics, Plovdiv, Bulgaria

Received: September 5, 2021 | Revised: September 19, 2021 | Accepted: September 30, 2021

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.6402953

Abstract

Human resource management is currently undergoing key changes. Like every element of social life, the role of effective work with staff is becoming key to vital for any organization. The development focuses on the possibilities by seeking a new vision for adapting human resource management to changes and dynamics of the environment, to obtain positive results in an organizational context. New approaches to governance have been gaining momentum in most developed countries in the last decade and cover both business and public administration.

Key words: human resource management, changes, crises, efficiency, good practices.

Introduction

Crisis situations and effective human resources management in a modern context are a key relationship in management. In this regard, a number of new challenges have emerged in recent years to address. New opportunities and key competences in modern governance have come to the fore. In a new way, solutions are sought in the field of leadership, change and motivating employees.

The need for the study is justified by a number of new management challenges, as well as the lack of practical developments in the field of comparative HRM. This need is also justified by new challenges, including rapid changes, crisis situations, economic factors and other.

The aim of this development is to identify key ideas and practices applicable in the modern organisation in the context of crisis management and to identify them as suitable for use in practice, thereby supporting a number of new challenges in management. Likewise, the academic society, especially the students in the fields of security and public administration studies will have a prompt manual for their learning and research.

Material and methods

The main method of the research is a view of some key publications available spots of expertise in human resource matters and other references and their short presentation in the article with two main goals – their distinct indication and their supplementation of each other in the human resource management matters. The method of the research of the article is also a comparative analysis and differences of interpretation by the court and their application in practice.

The materials analysed are in the following key areas: human resource management; organizational behavior; teambuilding; leadership; motivation and esc. Analytical materials and websites of public institutions have also been used, with proven good practices in the field of HRM.

Results

The identification of good practices and ideas in the publication are justified and classified in the definition of the survey categories. Appropriately summarised new ideas for effective human

resources management are provided. A key result and a particularly important value of the study is the presented good practices and summarized new theoretical components, as well as the ideas for their easier approbation through their good description.

Discussion

Modern determinants in human resource management

The main impetus caused by globalization was the recognition of the fact that improvements in the efficiency of organizations are closely related to the human factor, and hence to the practices of pay and employment, selection, working methods, staff relations, motivational policy and other aspects of personnel management (Vasilev, V. & Ognynski, D., 2020, p. 91-93). Therefore, staff, human resources in the era of a globalizing society are treated as capital, which in turn requires careful and innovative management. In this direction, the pandemic environment, as a result of Covid-19, had a detrimental effect on many ongoing processes of updating the theoretical framework in management processes (Marinov, R., 2018, p. 1-2).

Personnel management is undergoing a significant evolution in terms of changing and globalizing markets and focuses on innovative and practical actions, with the main goal of adapting to the changing environment in which organizations operate (Gigauri, I., 2021, p. 3).

New approaches to governance have been gaining momentum in most developed countries in the last decade, and cover both business and public services (Icheva, M., 2020, p. 210). The main impetus caused by globalization was the recognition of the fact that improvements in the efficiency of organizations are closely related to the human factor, and hence to the practices of pay and employment, selection, working methods, staff relations, motivational policy and other aspects of personnel management (Vasilev, V., 2021, p. 126). Therefore, staff, human resources in the era of a globalizing society are treated as capital, which in turn requires careful and innovative management. On the other hand, such a finding supports the conclusion that managers need to be given significantly more power and autonomy to manage their staff. On the other hand, globalization is also putting pressure on human resources management to be adapted more closely to the specific circumstances of different organizations, and that much more attention needs to be paid to developing comprehensive strategies for personnel management, staff needs planning, leadership skills development and staff motivation.

The globalizing society and business have exacerbated some factors influencing management processes. Factors such as: labor market pressure, accounting for equality and social justice and responsibility, demographic factors, the increased need for decentralization were presented to new leaders in the business and public spheres. These factors have increased their influence under the pressure of globalization and have clearly changed their influence on organizations.

At the heart of this process are the well-defined working conditions in the organization, preferred by talented people, namely:

- creating conditions for continuous improvement of employees For this purpose it is necessary to invest significantly in staff training, to work on projects that challenge the development of knowledge and skills, to develop and improve the roles of positions, to seek the competence approach in solving the problems in the organization / a good example in Bulgaria in this direction is the Municipality of Bansko, Bulgaria, with the “Center for Human Resources Development” built by it through an electronic platform (Municipality of Bansko, 2021) as well as the Municipality of Sandanski, Bulgaria, where a website for civil debates has been developed and operates (Municipality of Sandanski, 2021), as well as a number of other practices, described in detail in various initiatives and competitions at the national level (Institute of Public Administration, 2021);

- preferred organizations work with very demanding performance appraisal systems, rewarding and raising according to employee performance (Vasilev, V. & Stefanova, D., 2016., p. 389). In this regard, extremely good results are given by the various innovative approaches for employee motivation (e.g. – motivational banks; motivational posters; motivational diagnostics and others);

- a culture of risk-taking is built in the organization. In this regard, the role of leadership is of great importance, as well as the implementation of causal initiatives to present the positives of the work of the organization;
- organizations preferred by talented people adhere to strict standards for hiring, evaluating and developing their employees;
- employers who are profitable and developing and can provide good working and living conditions for their employees are preferred.

With the ever-increasing average age of the population, the public sector and businesses need to adapt their employment policies to ensure that they recruit and retain qualified staff. In the past, public organizations have watched indifferently as business organizations attract talented civil servants with the higher pay they offer (Stanin, M., 2020, p.163). As the extent and content of governance reforms vary from country to country, there are a number of important commonalities highlighting new trends in personnel management in the context of globalization in several directions and ideas (Vasilev, V., 2021, p. 124-125):

- *innovative approaches in management and wide application of “Job Shadowing”;*
- *organizational concentration on innovations in the management of newly recruited employees;*
- *emphasis on training and professional development, management of results and achievements;*
- *development of new forms of leadership.*

As can be seen from the above trends, modern organizations are throwing down the gauntlet of challenges through changes in management style (Vasilev, V. & Dimitrova, Sn., 2017, p. 5-6). This list does not cover all the challenges of governance in the context of globalization, but it is a good starting point for reflection in the search for answers to these and other problematic areas.

Innovative approaches in management and wide application of “Job Shadowing”

An interesting and modern component of motivation can be “Job Shadowing” – a technique that is a method of adaptation, widely used internationally. This method consists of the fact that the trainee is accompanied and becomes a “shadow” of an experienced employee in a real work environment, followed by it as a “shadow” during the working day. The trainer has the opportunity to discuss work situations not only with the employee to whom the “shadow” appears, but also with other team members, and receives feedback from everyone. In the foreign language, literature Shadowing is seen as a way to optimize the social capital of the organization and leadership development, it is established not only as an innovative method of employee training, but also as a direction in the training of future managers, but also a means to continuously increase efficiency activities in the organization as a whole.

Job Shadowing includes the following three stages:

1. Preparatory stage. At this stage, the “mentor” and the trainee define the learning objectives and desired outcomes, define their roles, and choose work situations to become a source of new experience for the trainee, providing opportunities to learn and acquire habits and skills.
2. Implementation of the training project. The trainee monitors the behavior of the “mentor” in the work environment and situations.
3. Post-project activities – After the implementation of the project, the participants gather to discuss and evaluate the results.

In some literature sources the following positive factors are derived, allowing the Shadowing method to become an effective tool for developing the potential of the organization and employees.

1. The organizational reality, the real work process is used as a training ground, as a “training laboratory”. The “mentor” and the “shadow” are involved in the work process, they are members of a team and learn from each other's experience.
2. The training is based on practice. In the process of Shadowing, the main elements of effective adult learning are brought together: gained real experience, reasoning / reflection / and discussion / feedback /.

3. Constant feedback between “mentor” and learner.

4. The expert knowledge of the “mentor” becomes more understandable for the learner. The learner is observed (and in some cases takes part) in the process of making managerial decisions, planning and others.

Organizational concentration on innovative approaches to the management of newly recruited employees

Although there are attempts in this regard, there are still serious gaps and weaknesses in the adaptation of newly appointed staff. In recent years, this emphasis has been placed in the context of crisis management. An important element in management in the new century will be to emphasize an old weakness in organizations, namely, incompetent work with newly appointed employees (Icheva, M. & Vasilev, V., 2021, p. 913-914).

Like any element of personnel management, the selection and appointment of employees is of particular importance. Given that globalization provides extremely great opportunities for mobility of candidates and for frequent job changes, one of the main driving wheels in the process of retaining employees is the period of recruitment and adaptation of new recruits. A serious challenge for organizations is the development and establishment of unique systems for this purpose (Vasilev, V., Stefanova, D. & Cherkezov, V., 2019, p. 111-113). A number of methods have gained popularity, with mentoring systems standing out as part of the organization’s training system.

Emphasis on training, professional development and management of results and achievements

The development of the skills and abilities of employees is a major goal of organizations in the age of globalization.

There are several main reasons that come to the fore when it comes to an increased emphasis on employee training and professional development. The needs are usually indicated: to provide employees and managers with the necessary skills to cope with their newly delegated responsibilities; to keep pace with the growing body of knowledge and skills required in a globalizing society; to improve the standards of service provision and to focus on the client; to achieve adaptation to modern technologies and to develop systems to facilitate this process and others. In general, training and professional development programs will be increasingly perceived and will play an important role in setting new values and achieving the desired changes in organizational culture in the age of globalization. Integrating staff training and professional development with organizations' strategies is also seen as a new type of challenge. There is a tendency for organizations to try to be part of more flexible training and development systems. Good examples in this regard are the contractual relations signed between municipal administrations of cities and universities and faculties, including the preparation of curricula and courses for employees, as well as the development of joint studies and projects, including in the field of security and security systems (Stoykov, S., 2018; p. 1-3).

Developing new forms of leadership through human resource management

Management in the context of globalization will require the emergence and development of new forms of leadership in organizations. This need arises for several reasons. First, organizations face the challenge of working in a multicultural environment that they usually do not know well, which is undoubtedly linked to security systems to some extent (Berchev, D. & Stefanov, M., 2019, p. 1457). Next, leaders will be required to send very “powerful” messages to employees, given that one of the most difficult tasks of human resource management is to retain employees in the age of globalization. Last but not least, human resource management will have more and more direct access to the most valuable capital of the organization - human. And for this reason, the most effective ways to increase this value of capital will be sought. There is a tendency for organizations to develop “transcultural leadership” (Chankova, D. & Vasilev, V., 2020, p. 211-212).

The increasing internationalization of business, in which multinational companies regularly do business around the world, combined with the growing diversity of the workforce, generally means that leaders must be trained and prepared for this new challenge. Increasingly popular is a model of leadership training that assumes that future leaders will need, among other established qualities, to be

trained in the following areas: *Development of global consciousness; Emotional intelligence and interpersonal skills; Socially responsible organizational behavior and “green” human resource management; Development of adaptability and sensitivity to diversity issues; Community and team building skills; Construction and application of internal communication systems* (Vasilev, V. & Arabadzjieva, V., 2020, p.2-3).

Conclusions

The balance between goals, plans and results in a dynamic environment for the development of the development system of an organization on the other hand is maintained by this part of the management functions, as goal setting, which is carried out in the public interest in accordance with public and international values, rules and regulations. It includes the use of force and management, which provides a realistic definition of needs, maintenance and improvement of existing and development of future capabilities, which is denoted by the term *strategic management*, including related to human resource management (Vasilev, V., 2020, p. 229-230).

Strategic management is a management process necessary for the organization to move from the state in which it finds itself to the desired state (i.e., to realize its successful movement towards the future). It includes strategic decisions (they are long-term in nature) and strategic actions that are applied to formulate and implement strategies that ensure coherence in the system and between it and its environment, allowing to achieve the set goals (Manolov, L., 2020, p.43).

Following Einstein’s maxim that “it is not possible to deal with the problem using the same type of thinking that brought this problem”, the future integrated model aimed at crisis management will turn the security of our society from a problem to a solution, only if it is created through scientific substantiation and analytically substantiated technology, indisputably reflecting on the management of human resources (Tepavicharova, M., & Boykova, L., 2016, p. 642).

Because the successful integrated model must contain the knowledge and abilities of people with integration thinking in it and for it, and not obedient performers whose mathematical knowledge has reached the level of simple arithmetic operation – “cuts” guaranteeing them a place in the teams to conduct the task. on the near election horizon next consecutive review of goals and objectives.

The role of human resource management is increasingly important. Undoubtedly, “... the people who are at the forefront must find their own personal successful style. Ultimately, leadership is as much a journey to yourself. It means being aware of yourself. Any style can lead them to the right end point.”

We will end with the words of the great writer Stephen King: “... because talent does not stand still, it simply does not know how to stand still – whether it is a talent for opening safes, reading thoughts or dividing ten-digit numbers in the mind, he shouts to be used. He never shuts up. He will wake you from your deepest sleep, shouting, Use me! Use me! Use me! Use me! I'm tired of sitting idle!”

It is in the described prerequisites for the effectiveness of human resource management in crisis situations are part of the answers in defining a new vision in the management of these relationships, seeking and at the same time offering high commitment and emphasis on talented employees.

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